

The First Australian Trained Doctors. Patrick Moloney (1843-1904). Part Two: Moloney and the Melbourne Hospital

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Abstract:

Dr Moloney was one of the first two graduates from an Australian Medical School. Part one of the history of Moloney detailed his clinical career. This part two deals with his appointments to the Melbourne Hospital, his forthright relationship with management, the clinical inpatient workload and clinical meetings and the unusual 'comfort' prescriptions. The development of the Melbourne Hospital as an outstanding clinical and educational medical establishment is also outlined. Some controversial issues from his career appear again when related to the hospital and medical education.

Keywords: *history, Australian medicine, Patrick Moloney, career, Melbourne Hospital.*

Appointments

On leaving the University, Dr. Moloney was appointed resident surgeon to the Melbourne Hospital. The Melbourne Hospital appointments were normally for five years, however, the Committee of the Melbourne Hospital dismissed Moloney from his office of resident surgeon for the offence of transgressing a disused rule, requiring the resident medical staff not be absent for more than three hours and to be indoors by 11.00pm even if off-duty.

The Argus criticised the management for treating grown men with high qualifications as school boys, good boys at a traditional boys boarding school. The Argus considered this decision should have been in the hands of senior doctors not administrators with as the Argus put it, skills in tea tasting and quilting! Dr William

Rees also resigned in support, but the committee initially would not change their mind.

However, although Rees departed for a position in Adelaide, Moloney reapplied for the now vacant position of resident physician and curiously the Melbourne Hospital Committee not only accepted his application but unanimously reappointed him to the hospital! Moloney was employed there until 1873. A bizarre volte-face perhaps triggered by the media comments, or the luck of the Irish (The Argus, 1868a; The Age, 1868a; The Herald, 1868)!

Dr. Moloney was one of the applicants for the position of physician to the Melbourne Hospital. When the result of the election was announced Moloney had the most votes of the eight candidates from the hospital subscribers and was therefore appointed honorary physician at the hospital, a position he held until 1898. Election

by subscribers continued until 1910 when the popularity vote was replaced to appointment on ability by a medical committee.

The Argus editorial, reproduced below, was unimpressed by this vote which appeared to rate Moloney on his popular celebrity status rather than years of experience and wisdom. Presumably, few electors were professional experts. It considered this would not have happened in famous British hospitals like the author's alma mater, The Middlesex Hospital. Observers of today will note a parallel with elections in USA!

Dr. P. Moloney, a young practitioner, who has only recently, comparatively speaking, taken his degree, heads the poll, while two physicians of high standing and long practice, like Drs. Jas. Robertson and J. B. Motherwell, occupy the second and third places respectively. We must not be understood as wishing to disparage Dr. Moloney, who is a gentleman of ability and promise, with an honourable and prosperous career before him, we trust. But he himself can scarcely fail to perceive that his position on the poll is due to factitious circumstances, and that much to his own regret, let us hope, it involves an undeserved slight and casts a gratuitous slur upon the two gentlemen who have been placed beneath him, and who are so much his seniors and superiors.

Dr. Moloney and the other members of the faculty will scarcely require to be reminded that if such an incident could have occurred in connexion with a hospital like Guy's, or St. Thomas's, or the Middlesex, or with the Hotel Dieu in Paris, the medical profession in both countries would have been scandalised by the incident. The displacement of a physician of the highest eminence, or the assignment to him of a secondary position, while the first was taken possession of by an almost unknown junior, is a thing which, fortunately, could not happen in any of the great hospitals in Europe, and ought not to be allowed to occur in the largest and most important institution of the kind in Australia. (The Herald, 1875; Geelong Advertiser, 1875; The Argus, 1875c; The Argus, 1875a).

Moloney was re-elected as Honorary Physician to the Melbourne Hospital gaining the most

votes from the governors and subscribers. Unusually by today's mores, the candidates advertised their candidacy in the press. Moloney stating:

'Dr Moloney is a candidate for the re-election as Honorary Physician to the Melbourne Hospital and begs to solicit the vote and interest of the governors and subscribers.'

An effort had been made to influence the election by publishing a record of the number of visits paid by the successful candidates of last election (The Herald, 1879; The Argus, 1879c; The Argus, 1879d).

Dr. Springthorpe related the successes of the Melbourne Hospital as a clinical school. Since 1862, when Dr. P. Moloney and Dr. W. C Rees entered as medical students, the school had grown until eighteen years later there were one hundred and sixty students attached to it. Two hundred students had graduated. The Alumni included three professors and two lecturers. Twenty doctorates and four masters degrees had been granted. Ten of the honouraries and sixty nine junior staff were alumni. Many other Australian hospitals were largely staffed by Melbourne graduates. Distinguished successes in eighteen years (Table Talk, 1880).

Dr Moloney announced his candidacy for re-election to the office of honorary physician to the: Melbourne Hospital, a position which he has held for the last eight years. He was subsequently elected in first position with one thousand three hundred and sixty seven council votes (Williamstown Chronicle, 1883; The Argus, 1883c).

The Managing Committee of the Melbourne hospital appointed Dr Aitcheson, one of the three newly appointed resident medical officers, to Dr Moloney. They reported that Moloney treated eighty eight inpatients in the previous month (The Argus, 1884f).

A deputation from the council of the University yesterday met a sub-committee of the Melbourne Hospital and members of the medical profession in the boardroom of the institution to discuss what arrangements should be made for formal clinical tuition of the medical

students. The doctors considered that payment and university titles would be anticipated. The majority were enthusiastic at being involved in tuition medical and considered that a formal program should be drawn up.

Dr Moloney said the appointment of half the staff as clinical teachers would make the students too respectful to those who were appointed and disrespectful to those who were not, perhaps reflecting his lack of enthusiasm for teaching and concern for his status and private practice (The Argus, 1885b).

The University Council, headed by the chancellor, the Bishop of Melbourne and the vice chancellor, Dr Brownless appointed examiners from the clinical staff. Dr Moloney was appointed examiner in obstetric medicine and diseases of women and children (The Argus, 1885c).

The adjourned meeting of the Melbourne University council appointed Dr Moloney a lecturer in surgery. Curious today that he should be employed as a physician, lecture in surgery and examine in obstetrics (The Age, 1885b).

Dr Moloney applied for one of the positions as honorary physician to inpatients, a post he had held for the past twelve years and advertised for support in the press. In the subsequent ballot he was successful receiving the most votes (Herald, 1887a; 1887b; The Argus, 1887).

Dr. P. Moloney intimated that he was a candidate for re-election as physician to inpatients at the Melbourne Hospital in the forthcoming election. He was successfully re-elected, though the press disapproved of the current method in which success depending upon the amount of advertising that each of the candidates utilised (Advocate, 1891b; The Herald, 1891).

Disease Management

The physicians of Melbourne Hospital discussed the optimum management of cases of scarlet fever following an outbreak in Melbourne. Dr. Moloney who had not been present at the meeting of physicians, wrote that his experience

was strongly against the aggregation of scarlatina patients. He thought initial isolation to be of benefit, but with regard to his own cases, he would prefer having them treated in the general wards (The Argus, 1875b)

A letter from Dr. Moloney informed the hospital committee that patients suffering from measles were being admitted into the hospital, and not separated in any way from the other resident patients. Plans were made to erect an isolation unit.

This is in an era when the fatality rate in children under five was 10% and under nine months, as high as 25%. It is estimated that fifty seven million lives have been saved globally by vaccination this century, however some one hundred and thirty six thousand measles deaths occurred in 2022 with fourteen percent of children being unvaccinated, an optional disease likely to become more common in this antivaccination period (The Age, 1880b)!

A letters was read from Drs. Moloney and Williams at the weekly meeting of the managing committee of the Melbourne Hospital on the subject of admitting lunatic patients into the hospital. They considered this was undesirable as the hospital accommodation was inadequate, and the nurses were without the special training requisite for their treatment. Further, the presence of lunatic patients in the ordinary wards was detrimental to the recovery of the other patients. The opinion was endorsed by the committee.

The issue resonates today where professional health care workers are not provided with adequate protection from violent psychiatric patients (The Argus, 1881b).

Annual Leave and Sick Leave

Dr. Moloney requested an additional week's leave of absence which was granted (The Argus, 1870).

Dr. Moloney was granted further leave of absence for ten days. The secretary reported the hospital information for a week, there were fifty nine admissions, two hundred and twenty nine

new outpatients, two hundred and fifty casualties, a total of five hundred and thirty eight. Following sixty four discharges and nine deaths, there were three hundred and forty four inpatients (The Age, 1876).

Moloney commenced three weeks leave of absence from the Melbourne Hospital from five days previously. He was a passenger on the *Southern Cross* bound for Launceston and returned three weeks later on the *Mangana* (The Age, 1879b; Weekly Times, 1879; Advocate, 1879; The Argus, 1879d).

The committee of the Melbourne Hospital received a letter from Dr. Moloney informing the committee that he had been absent for the last fortnight suffering from an unspecified illness, during which time another gentleman had acted as locum tenens, but that next week he would be able to resume duties. (The Age, 1880c).

Dr Moloney was noted by the Melbourne Hospital management committee as having leave of absence owing to illness (The Argus, 1881a).

Dr. Moloney was granted leave of absence from his position as honorary medical officer for three week at the ordinary weekly meeting of the management committee of the Melbourne Hospital. The following day he departed for New Zealand aboard the SS Wairarapa of 1,023 tons (The Age, 1883a; The Argus, 1883d).

Dr Moloney applied for leave of absence for a fortnight at the ordinary weekly meeting of the Melbourne Hospital management committee (The Argus, 1883c).

Dr Moloney requested three weeks annual leave from the ordinary fortnightly meeting of the Melbourne Hospital management committee (The Age, 1885a).

The Melbourne Hospital management committee granted leave of absence for twelve months to Dr Moloney (The Herald, 1886).

Hospital Statistics

The secretary reported that there were fifty three admissions, sixty one discharges and four deaths.

One hundred and forty six new patients were seen in outpatients and two hundred and seven in casualty (The Age, 1872; Melbourne Punch, 1872; The Herald, 1872).

The secretary of the Melbourne Hospital informed the committee of the cost of diet and extras issued to patients by each of the honorary staff during the month of February. Dr Moloney saw eighty nine patients at a cost to the hospital of £60 1s 8d. The point of this statement remained obscure (Weekly Times, 1878).

Dr Moloney was reported to have made thirty two visits to the Melbourne Hospital during the last fifteen weeks while on holiday for three weeks by the hospital committee. Moloney complained that he had made ten more visits than the committee's figure, and that this figure gave no idea of the number of patients seen or the work involved. He considered the honorary medical staff were too few. He had, for example usually more than fifty beds occupied, and allowing three minutes to each bed, his round occupied three hours, which made a large encroachment on one engaged in private practice.

The chairman noted there were only eight honorary staff compared with four years previously. It was also noted visits were counted by front door entrances while Moloney frequently entered via the back door. Drs. Hewitt, Robertson, Motherwell and Fitzgerald subsequently intimated that they thought the present staff large enough for the work which had to be done. Administration stated that during the past week there were seventy six admissions, two hundred and thirty eight new cases seen in the outpatients, two hundred and thirty one patients in the casualty department for a total of five hundred and forty five new patients There were seven deaths and eighty seven discharges leaving three hundred and twenty nine inpatients. This is a considerable work load for only eight consultants (The Argus, 1879a; The Age, 1879a; The Age, 1879c).

The Melbourne Hospital figures for the week were number of inpatients eighty nine, twenty six admissions making a total of one hundred and fifteen, thirteen discharges, two deaths,

leaving ninety five inpatients. Two hundred and twelve patient attended the outpatient clinic and twenty four visited casualty, for a total of three hundred and thirty one.

E. Wheeler, an eight year old boy was admitted with diphtheria. Though he suffered rather considerably on the day of admission, the attack was not a severe one, and the patient was progressing favourably (The Age, 1880a).

Table 1. Dr Moloney’s Monthly Inpatient Numbers 1878 - 1887

DATE	NUMBER OF INPATIENTS	REFERENCE
February 1878	89	Weekly Times 9/3/1878
October 1881	16	The Age 12/1/1881
November 1881	23	The Age 12/1/1881
December 1881	18	The Age 12/1/1881
June 1882	74	The Age 5/7/1882
July 1882	74	The Age 9/8/1882
August 1882	72	The Age 6/9/1882
September 1882	68	The Argus 10/10/1882
December 1882	80	The Age 5/1/1883
March 1883	91	The Argus 12/4/1883
April 1883	90	The Argus 9/5/1883
May 1883	91	The Argus 6/6/1883
June 1883	67	The Argus 11/7/1883
August 1883	76	Melbourne Punch 13/9/1883
December 1883	61	Gippsland Times 9/1/1884
February 1884	77	Leader 8/3/1884
June 1884	76	The Age 31/7/1884
October 1884	81	The Agus 12/11/1884
January 1885	78	The Argus 12/2/1885
February 1885	87	The Age 12/3/1885
March 1885	94	The Argus 8/4/1885
April 1885	82	The Argus 6/5/1885
June 1885	75	The Age 15/7/1885
August 1885	92	The Argus 10/9/1885
September 1885	82	The Argus 8/10/1885
November 1885	80	The Argus 19/12/1885
July 1887	88	The Age 27/8/1887

The ordinary weekly meeting of the committee of management of the Melbourne Hospital reported that Dr Moloney’s seventy four patients comfort prescriptions were two hundred and twenty two brandy’s, eight hundred wines, ninety gins, thirty two whiskys and fifty nine lemonades (The Age, 1882a).

The ordinary weekly meeting of the committee of management of the Melbourne Hospital reported Moloney treated seventy two patients and prescribed them four hundred and six brandy’s, three hundred and fifty one wines, three hundred and thirty six gins, thirty two rums and twenty six lemonades (The Age, 1882b).

The Ballarat Courier published an editorial stating ‘on glancing at the quantities of alcohol ordered for their patients, one becomes confused aa to the distinction between publican and physician (The Ballarat Courier, 1882)!

The ordinary weekly meeting of the committee of the Melbourne Hospital informed that three cases of erysipelas had been admitted to the institution, the circumstances of the patients rendering such a course necessary. During the month of October twelve cases were discharged cured or relieved after surgical operations. Two cases died after being operated on, death being due in one case to the original injury, and in the

other to pyaemia, a reflexion of the dangers of surgery with limited sterility and no antibiotics.

Dr. Moloney's figures for the month were sixty eight patients, who were prescribed three hundred and twenty seven ounces of brandy, one hundred and twenty seven ounces of wine, eighteen ounces of whisky, and one hundred and seventy nine bottles of lemonade as comfort measures (The Argus, 1882).

The Age commented on the extremely variable amount of alcohol prescribed by various doctors in the Melbourne Hospital noting that superficially the mortality rates were lower for patients treated by doctors who prescribed most alcohol. However, showing an early awareness of epidemiology and statistical confounders, the Age considered that a comparison was only relevant when treating patients with similar conditions.

Dr. Moloney's eighty patients were noted to receive five hundred and thirty three tots of brandy and three hundred and twenty four of wine.

The Age concluded that startling difference of treatment disclosed in these figures can only be explained by supposing that outside the text books, personal whim or predilection enters almost as largely into the treatment of disease as the formulated principles of science (The Age, 1883b).

The ordinary weekly meeting of the committee of the Melbourne Hospital reported that Dr Moloney's ninety one patients for the month were prescribed a total of one thousand five hundred and thirteen tots of alcohol as comfort measures (The Argus, 1883a)!

The ordinary weekly meeting of the committee of management of the Melbourne Hospital reported Moloney treated sixty seven inpatients the previous month and the hospital as a whole admitted sixty new in patients, saw one hundred and sixty four outpatients, and seventy eight casualties for a total of three hundred and two cases. There were nine deaths and fifty discharges leaving two hundred and eighty six patients (Argus, 1883e).

Dr Moloney was reported to have cared for fifty one inpatients during the previous month by the usual weekly meeting of the Melbourne Hospital committee (The Argus, 1883b).

The Punch had another satirical article of the prescribing of alcohol by the Melbourne Hospital Doctors. "The next on the list is our old friend, Dr. Patrick Moloney (and a right good fellow, too). He warmed up 73 sick people during the month, with 342 ounces of brandy, 22 of wine, 62 of gin, and 6 bottles of lemonade and soda water. This is the "mixed" treatment. We ourselves have often tried this style of getting well, outside the hospital, but it has not resulted favourably. Indeed, we may say that on one occasion the consequences were, "fined forty shillings, and take him away."

If Dr. Fulton is out at the time we call, then we shall favour Doctor Moloney with our disease. And we shall think all the more highly of him if he will prescribe cigarettes amongst his comforts. As he knows himself, they are absolute necessities' (Melbourne Punch, 1883).

Dr Moloney was reported to have attended sixty one inpatients during the previous month at the usual weekly meeting of the Melbourne Hospital management committee.

At a meeting of the hospital committee a letter was read from a patient named Bridget Kelly, of North Sandridge, complaining of Dr. Montgomery. The letter stated that the woman had been an outpatient of the hospital for some months past, under the care of Dr. Griffiths. On the 28th of December she was entered as an inpatient. On the 29th Dr. Montgomery ordered her to get up and put her clothes on, saying he would make an outdoor patient of her, and send her back to Dr. Griffiths.

She answered she was not able to go, and on the following day Dr. Montgomery again told her to go out, and he and the nurse laughed at her. She refused to go out, and Dr. Montgomery became enraged, and on her stating her intention to appeal to Dr. Moloney, he said that gentleman had nothing to do with it. Next day Dr. Montgomery took down the diet card, and the nurse threatened that if she did not leave she would be dragged out. On the 4th January she

saw Dr. Griffiths, who gave her another order to go back into the hospital, but Dr. Montgomery refused to admit her on that order. The letter of complaint was referred to the medical superintendent for report (Gippsland Times, 1884).

The ordinary weekly meeting of the committee of management of the Melbourne Hospital noted that Dr Moloney's sixty-one patients for the previous month received six hundred and thirty one brandies and other comfort measures (The Argus, 1884a).

Dr. Moloney, after careful examination, condemned the whole of the stimulant medication sent to the Melbourne Hospital for the use of the patients as 'comfort measures.'

The Custom House confirmed Dr. Moloney's condemnation of the samples (The Age, 1884a).

The usual weekly meeting of the Melbourne Hospital management committee noted that Dr Moloney attended seventy seven patients for the previous month (Leader, 1884a).

A serious charge was brought by the medical students against Dr Moloney, one of the honorary physicians. They complained to the committee that, though they have been attending regularly since April 1st, Moloney has not attended once to give them that clinical instruction for which they had to pay him fees to the amount of £4 10 each. It appeared that in fact Dr Moloney had only attended at the hospital for five hours during the whole of the past month.

The committee awaited the receipt of an explanation from Dr Moloney. It was resolved to appoint an additional medical officer at £150 per annum.

Dr. Moloney wrote in reference to the complaints that had been made against him, to the effect that for some time past he had found it more convenient to visit the hospital in the afternoon, and he was under the impression that the students had arranged to attend the clinical lectures of the other physicians. However, in reply to a letter from some of the fourth year students, he would make arrangements for regularly resuming his morning attendances. .

For the past three weeks he had been able to attend in the forenoon, and he declared to say that he would always be glad to assist the committee in furthering the interests of the hospital (The Argus, 1884d; Leader, 1884b; The Argus, 1884c; The Age, 1884b).

A senior student of the Melbourne Hospital and Melbourne University Medical School wrote a letter to the Argus in view of recent adverse correspondence stating there was in fact an abundance of clinical cases and of doctors more than willing to impart their wisdom and experience on the wards. While citing many specific most helpful doctors, he wrote of Moloney;

'At the beginning of the year Dr Moloney was unable to attend the hospital in the morning owing to private duties, but at the request of his students he made other arrangements, and I believe attends now at his appointed time.'

Faint praise (The Argus, 1884g)!

The ordinary fortnightly meeting of the Melbourne Hospital managing committee reported that eighty six inpatients were allocated to Dr Moloney (The Argus, 1885a).

Originally called the Melbourne Hospital and situated in a 10-bed, two-storey cottage on the corner of Lonsdale and Swanston Streets, the hospital expanded and was then completely rebuilt on that site in 1913. It moved to its present location on Grattan Street in 1944 but remnants of the old buildings still exist on its original site within the QV Centre.

The hospital was renamed the Royal Melbourne Hospital by Royal Charter on 27 March 1935. Today, His Majesty King Charles III is the Royal Patron of the Royal Melbourne Hospital.

A conference took place between the committee and the honorary medical and surgical staff of the Melbourne Hospital on the question of the desirableness of removing the institution to another venue. Dr Moloney said that the faults of construction in the hospital were too numerous to mention. Patients with phthisis did u badly in it as a rule He had known thirteen patients to die in one day in the institution and four patients had died in one day on one bed All

over the hospital the death rate was one in six. Such a death rate in a man's private practice would ruin his reputation!

One would expect doctor's reputation should depend equally on the outcome of all patients rather than public or private status assuming one cared equally for all (The Argus, 1886)!

The usual fortnightly meeting of the Melbourne Hospital management committee noted that Dr. Moloney had resumed duty (The Age, 1887b).

The ordinary meeting of the Melbourne Hospital committee reported that Dr Moloney's eighty eight patients received as 'comfort measures, one thousand and twenty four brandy's eight hundred and eighty six wines, eighty four whisky's and forty six ales (The Age, 1887a).

At the annual meeting of the governors of the Melbourne Hospital, Dr. Moloney pointed out that the present site of the Melbourne Hospital was all that could be desired, being on the brow of a hill and well drained. However it was pointed out that the drainage from the hospital ran through the City in open channels, which was thought to be unsanitary and not a good thing for the citizens.

The chairman, Mr. F. R. Godfrey referred to the adverse criticism which had been passed by members of the medical staff on the management of the hospital. Members of the medical staff had made damaging statements in private about the percentage of deaths of the cases treated by each surgeon These calculations were not so favourable to some doctors as to others.

It was considered that the surgeons would probably be able to vindicate themselves but were not always successful. It was considered the esprit among the doctors ensured they kept their mouths shut when difficulties arose (Weekly Times, 1890).

An extensive series of articles in the press referred to the recent outbreak of diphtheria in which three people died including one Melbourne Hospital Nurse after caring for one of the other cases. Apparently Nurse Carter complained that she was neglected by the other

nursing staff prior to her demise according to a report by Dr. Forster.

The Nurse was in Dr Moloney's ward. Forster asked Moloney if she may be administered champagne as a comfort measure. Moloney agreed with this and prescribed regular painting of her throat. Neither were given nor the milk she requested.

Dr Forster was denied admission to her ward by a porter acting on behalf on Dr Molloy, the superintendent, provoking some acrimonious exchange in the press. Moloney appears to emerge with an unsullied reputation for events on his watch after deflecting disapproval by suggesting a separate building for diphtheria patients, though the nurses were widely criticised (The Herald, 1890a; The Herald, 1890b; The Ballarat Star, 1890; The Herald, 1890c; The Herald, 1890d).

The fortnightly meeting of the committee of management of the Melbourne Hospital avoided planning for the advent of the first female graduates next year and the option of female house staff at present. Moloney applied for re-election as a physician to the inpatients (The Argus, 1891a).

The annual meeting of the subscribers to the Melbourne Hospital thanked Dr Moloney for his gift of pictures (The Argus, 1889).

Dr. Moloney was granted a fortnight's leave of absence at the ordinary meeting of the Melbourne Hospital management committee (The Age, 1889).

The Herald noted that it was the fortieth anniversary of Professor George Britten Halford.

M.D., the first Professor of Physiology and Anatomy of the University of Melbourne, now aged eighty, commencing his work with a class of three students in the newly-founded Medical School The three students were Patrick Moloney, and William Carey Rees, and the Rev. Alexander Mackie, both deceased (Herald, 1903).

Some Misdemeanours

The Melbourne Hospital appointments were normally for five years, however, the Committee of the Melbourne Hospital dismissed Moloney from his office of resident surgeon for the offence of transgressing a disused rule, requiring the resident medical staff not be absent for more than three hours and to be indoors by 11.00pm even if off-duty.

The Argus criticised the management for treating grown men with high qualifications as school boys, good boys at a traditional boys boarding school. The Argus considered this decision should have been in the hands of senior doctors not administrators with as the Argus put it, skills in tea tasting and quilting! Dr William Rees also resigned in support, but the committee initially would not change their mind.

However, although Rees departed for a position in Adelaide, Moloney reapplied for the now vacant position of resident physician and curiously the Melbourne Hospital Committee not only accepted his application but unanimously reappointed to the hospital! Moloney was employed there until 1873. A bizarre volte-face perhaps triggered by the media comments, or the luck of the Irish (The Argus, 1868a; The Age, 1868a; The Herald, 1868)!

The Melbourne Hospital Committee terminated Dr Moloney's contract for again being absent from the hospital after 11.00pm. The papers were fully of sarcastic comments about the talent of the administrators and their expectation that professional adults should not enjoy the festive season when off duty (Melbourne Punch, 1872; The Herald, 1872).

A serious charge was brought by the medical students against Dr Moloney, one of the honorary physicians. They complained to the committee that, though they have been attending regularly since April 1st, Moloney has not attended once to give them that clinical instruction for which they had to pay him fees to the amount of £4 10s each. It appeared that in fact Dr Moloney had only attended at the hospital for five hours during the whole of the past month.

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This is unimpressive for a man who superficially is an enthusiastic supporter of the University, the Medical School and education as a whole, a man who applied for and expected a position as a university lecturer.

He should have discovered what was happening with student teaching rather than assume it was happening. The allegation that he only attended public patients for five hours a month when he has dozens of patients under his care is appalling. It was not further pursued or commented upon (The Argus, 1884d; Leader, 1884b; The Argus, 1884b; The Age, 1884b).

By October 1888, Moloney had resigned from his honorary appointment to the regret of his hospital and appears to have retired after only twenty years' service. A financial option not available for physicians today! The Age noted Dr. Moloney was one of the two first medical graduates of the Melbourne University (The Age, 1898).

Dr Moloney was accused of neglect of one of his patients. Mr Arundel Carter, the coroner for the county of Middlesex, England, referring to the death of his sister, the above nurse in the Melbourne Hospital who died in August last from diphtheria, and stating that from the reports he had received from independent persons he was obliged to come to the

conclusion that the deceased had been neglected whilst ill.

The writer said his relative had complained of want of sufficient nourishment and added that he had also received reports of the lack of attention on the part of the hospital staff.

An extensive series of articles in the press referred to the recent outbreak of diphtheria in which three people died including the above Melbourne Hospital Nurse after caring for one of the other cases. Apparently Nurse Carter complained that she was neglected by the other nursing staff prior to her demise according to a report by Dr. Forster.

The Nurse was in Dr Moloney's ward. Forster asked Moloney if she may be administered champagne as a comfort measure. Moloney agreed with this and prescribed regular painting of her throat. Neither were given nor the milk she requested.

Dr Forster was denied admission to her ward by a porter acting on behalf on Dr Molloy, the superintendent, provoking some acrimonious exchange in the press. Moloney appears to emerge with an unsullied reputation for events on his watch after deflecting disapproval by suggesting a separate building for diphtheria patients, though the nurses were widely criticised. As medical men and women we owe it to our colleagues to ensure personally they receive the optimal care.

A letter was read from the chairman saying the matter had been fully inquired into at the time. Dr Moloney, who attended the case, said that there had been no neglect and that he was quite satisfied that the nurse had received every care. Dr Morton, the resident surgeon, informed the committee that he had visited the patient half a dozen times a day, and Dr Moloney, in whose care she was, had visited her three or four times daily

It was resolved to send the doctors reports to the writer, and also the report of the autopsy.

There may be no negligence here (The Herald, 1890a; The Herald, 1890b; The Ballarat Star, 1890; The Herald, 1890c; The Herald, 1890d; The Argus, 1891b; Advocate, 1891a).

Dr P. Moloney publicly criticised a medical colleague at the inquest into the death by drowning of Michael O'Brien, implying that the treatment by Dr Crowley was not so complete as it might have been, and that some slight delay took place. Dr Molloy, the medical superintendent denied the statements of Dr Moloney at the inquest and afterwards wrote to the president of the Hospital Committee with reference to the subject.

This resulted in the House Committee holding a special meeting chaired by the President, Mr F. Godfrey to deal with the matter. Drs Moloney, Molloy, and Crowley were also in attendance. The house committee found that there was no delay or improper treatment by Dr Crowley in dealing with the case of Michael O'Brien, and completely exonerated him from all blame.

They also expressed regret that if Dr Moloney entertained the opinion he expressed at the inquest that he did not refrain from expressing it at that place, and that he might instead have communicated it to the Hospital Committee.

This is a significant reprimand for unprofessional behaviour, a clear indication the Moloney's sense of self-importance exceeded his professional ethics. Finding fault with a colleague in public is unacceptable behaviour, especially when your allegations are baseless (The Herald, 1892).

Conclusion

Dr Moloney was an outstanding clinician, well respected in the development of the Melbourne Hospital as an outstanding clinical and educational establishment. He was well aware of his reputation and was not backward in expressing his opinion on many matters.

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